

Learning Body Movement Sonification in an Hour

Evaluating p5.js, MediaPipe, and WebAudioXML as a Pedagogical Platform

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ABSTRACT

Sonification in general, and sonification of body movements in particular, can be of great interest for different purposes, including research activities and artistic work. Up till recently, it has often been a time-consuming and sometimes expensive procedure to explore the field which can make sonification difficult for beginners to enter. The current study aims to solve these challenges by using radically inclusive and accessible technologies for learning and sharing sonification applications. It uses Google MediaPipe, the p5.js online editor, and WebAudioXML (WAXML) as a platform where it is possible to learn, create, and share sonification of body movements without having any earlier experiences from sonification, audio programming, or web development. The platform was evaluated during a one-hour workshop using observations and user responses through an online form. The result is promising and shows that web technologies work well on various computers and that all participants succeeded in meeting the goals for the workshop within the limited time. The answers from the online form also give insights into further development of platforms for learning sonification and ideas for new syntax and features for WAXML.

1 Introduction

Sonification of body movements is an area with great potential for research purposes as well as artistic work. By mapping real-time or recorded movement data to audio parameters and letting the data control a sound, it is possible to monitor relations between different body parts in dancing, walking, or various daily activities. The movement data can also be the material and driver for generating an artistic output by using the body movement data to control a digital musical instrument.

For both scientific and artistic purposes, the process of making the sonification typically requires a multi-disciplinary set of skills for data preparation, sound synthesis, mapping parameters and finally listening and tuning the settings [5]. It is also important to understand auditory perception [13] and have experience in sound design and musical composi-

tion to use the potential of sonification. These requirements make it difficult for beginners in both the artistic and engineering communities to get started with sonification and the barrier potentially hinders many from even trying. Sonification of body movements typically also often requires advanced and expensive technologies like sensors or MoCap systems to retrieve the data which makes it unsuitable for educational settings with larger student groups. This study aims to design, develop, and evaluate a set of tools that contributes to forming an accessible, flexible, and open platform for making workshops, tutorials, and courses for sonification applications. The platform was tested in a workshop as part of the Sound and Music Computing Summer School 2023.

In the following sections, related technologies and previous work will be presented and compared with the technologies used in this study, and the results from the workshop will be presented and discussed. Finally, some general conclusions are drawn from the project.

2 Background

Many applications and tools have been developed to facilitate the need for sonifying data [20, 3, 13, 15, 18] where the majority of the findings are shared through the International Community For Auditory Display (ICAD). Many of the earlier tools are not working anymore because they were made for operating systems that are no longer supported. Since Web Audio API¹ became a Web Recommendation 2021, there has been an increasing interest in exploring the possibilities of using web technologies for sonification purposes [4, 2, 8, 14] and Web Audio has proven to be an accessible, stable and very useful platform for learning and distributing interactive audio applications [9].

A strength often found in the tools for sonification is that they come with a predefined set of options for making the mapping from data to sound a straightforward process. While that often is a great help, it can arguably also limit the headroom for creative solutions, and many researchers and artists prefer to use more open programming tools like Max/MPS [16], Pure Data [17], and SuperCollider [11] to achieve their sonification goals.

The current study draws from the openness of the latter languages and benefits at the same time from being built with web technologies like some of the sonification tools mentioned above.

There are various ways of capturing body movements, including attached sensors [2] and motion capture (MoCap)

¹<https://www.w3.org/TR/webaudio/>

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Figure 1: A screenshot from p5.js showing the coding interface with the included files to the left, the WAXML syntax in the middle, and the graphical interface to the right.

systems [12], that give high-quality results but often are expensive and time-consuming to configure. New alternatives, using machine learning together with live-stream video from a webcam, offer new possibilities and have proven to be useful for sonification purposes [19]. The response time and measurement accuracy might not yet compete with sensors and MoCap systems, but the cost-efficiency and accessibility are factors that make the technology interesting for entry-level sonification projects like this.

The current version of the platform focuses on mapping real-time body movements to audio parameters but it could potentially be extended or modified to map any type of real-time or stored data to sound.

3 Technical description

In this section, the design goals behind the platform are presented and explained followed by a use case where the steps to build a simple sonification application with the tool are described.

3.1 Design

Initially, five goals formed the basis for the technical design of the platform:

The platform should...

- be web-based and run on both computers and mobile devices.
- have integrated support for capturing body movements.

- have an open and flexible audio configuration structure.
- take less than an hour for a beginner to get started, creating, and sharing a new sonification application.
- support the needs of both beginners and experts.

Earlier studies indicate that Google Mediapipe [10] serves well as a real-time body movement tracker [9] and that WAXML [6] is relatively easy to learn for beginners which made those two technologies suitable. WAXML is a descriptive language for configuring an audio routing graph with Web Audio API and has an extensive syntax for mapping values to audio parameters [7].

Earlier experiences with a tool where editing of the WAXML scripts was done in a basic HTML TextArea² suggested that it would be beneficial with better tools for debugging and error checking. This led to p5.js³, which is an online application for creative coding aimed at being accessible to everyone. The most important feature of p5.js compared to the earlier tool is that it allows the user to upload new files or replace the template files with their audio samples and scripts. The script editor also has an error-checking feature that warns if there are any errors in the WAXML code.

3.2 The platform

The platform built for this study offers a concept where different open web technologies like HTML, XML, CSS, and

²<https://hanslindetorp.github.io/waxml-lab>

³<https://p5js.org/>

JavaScript are combined with Google MediaPipe in the p5.js editor. This offers an accessible platform where sonification applications can be built using the WAXML language. One project in the editor can be compared with a template project in Max/MSP or Pure Data with a pre-configured webcam input and some core unit generators. One major difference, though, is that the audio programming is completely script-based in WAXML.

This section explains how the different technologies are integrated and how the platform can be used to sonify body movements.

A project in p5.js is called a ‘Sketch’ (see Figure 1). Each Sketch is a directory with HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and possibly other files. The files used in this study are structured as follows:

The HTML file contains the canvas element used for showing the webcam video. It also contains some custom HTML elements for various common audio visualizers and variable-inspectors. The HTML file can be edited to include any element of the users’ choice. The files in the script folder handle the integration of MediaPipe and WAXML and shall not be edited or removed for the Sketch to work. The CSS file contains the basic settings that control the size and position of the visual objects in the interface and can be edited to redesign the look of the application. Finally, the core file for this study is the audio.xml file where all audio configuration and parameter mappings are specified. This file shall be written using the WAXML syntax which is described briefly below and more in detail at <https://waxml.org>.

The p5.js environment offers the possibility to make collections of Sketches. For this particular study, six Sketches with different audio configurations were put together to form a step-by-step tutorial with a focus on how to map values from the webcam to different target audio parameters. All Sketches are available for testing at <https://waxml.org/link/collection-1>. The Sketches are organized according to complexity, where the first two are limited to only control the gain of an oscillator using one finger. The next two combine the positions of both hands controlling the cutoff frequency of a lowpass filter and the frequency of an oscillator. The last two Sketches introduce the concept of snapping pitches to a musical scale and also controlling spatial panning in a multi-channel speaker setup.

A typical procedure for a user to try out and modify a Sketch is to first select it from the collection and press PLAY in the p5.js editor to run it in the browser. The next step is to go through the code with comments in the audio.xml

file to understand how the audio objects and mappings are configured. To modify the Sketch, the user needs to make a duplicate, make the changes to the audio.xml file in the new Sketch, and then press PLAY to try it. The user can then share a fullscreen version of the sonification through a unique URL.

An example of a WAXML document including both variable mapping settings and an audio graph configuration can be seen in the middle section of the interface in Figure 1. This WAXML document shows a Sketch where three `<var>` elements are used to capture the position of the hands. The `<var>` elements also exemplify how the values from MediaPipe (ranging from 0 to 1) are mapped to values that are appropriate for the different audio parameters in Web Audio API.

The lower part of the script in the example contains a subtractive synthesizer with a sawtooth oscillator, a lowpass filter, and a gain control. These three unit generators are represented with one XML element each. This is a simple, monophonic synthesizer model, but it is possible to exchange the model with any audio configuration including external WebAssembly⁴ modules.

The configuration is set up for the landmarks in MediaPipe (33 for the body, 21 for each hand, and 478 for the face) so that all X and Y positions are updated in WAXML on every frame. This makes it possible to refer to them through a corresponding name (e.g. `"$rightHand8x"`).

3.3 WAXML syntax

WAXML has a syntax supporting most of the native Web Audio API nodes plus a collection of custom objects. It is possible to build synthesizers, mixing consoles, integrate Web Assembly objects, and more. There are also objects for mapping values, routing events, and positioning spatial audio.

WAXML has been developed through iterative phases with various artistic and research-based projects [12] and many features have been added to WAXML as a result of the needs of those projects. Most important for this study is the `<var>` element that acts similarly to a cell in a spreadsheet application. Its `value`-attribute can hold references to one or several variables from external sources and process real-time data using mathematical JavaScript expressions. The `<var>` element also has features for mapping in-data from any range to out-data in a new range using any combination of linear, logarithmic, step-wise, and mathematical mapping methods. It has also a built-in syntax for mapping between domains like MIDI note numbers and frequency.

Below is a basic example to illustrate the core concept of audio parameter mapping using WAXML.

In this particular example, the horizontal position of the right-hand index finger (`$rightHand8x`) is mapped to a value in hertz (aimed to control the frequency of an oscillator). The active `mapin` range is set to `"0.2, 0.8"` which means that only movements between 20% and 80% of the horizontal range of the screen are being recognized. The `mapout`-attribute is set to a list of values referring to MIDI note numbers in a musical scale. The `curve`-attribute is set to `"step"` to make the value step between the MIDI note numbers rather than interpolating between them, and finally,

⁴<https://webassembly.org/>

the `convert`-attribute applies a conversion of the MIDI note number to a frequency value in hertz.

The attributes in the `<var>` element work similarly to nodes in a graphical programming language where each line represents one transformation node. The order of the transformation is fixed and runs in the following order:

```
value > mapin > mapout > convert
```

The `<var>` element in this example is named "f1" and is used by the `frequency`-attribute of the `OscillatorNode` at the end of the script where "\$f1" is used to reference the `<var>` object.

```
<var
  name="f1"
  default="100"
  value="$rightHand8x"
  mapin="0.2,0.8"
  mapout="60,62,63,65,67,69,71,72"
  curve="step"
  convert="MIDI->frequency" />
<OscillatorNode frequency="$f1"/>
```


Figure 2: The incoming value represented on the x-axis as specified by the `value`-attribute (in this case, the horizontal position of the right-hand index finger). Time is represented on the y-axis with the current time at the top and the curve animating downwards.

Figure 3: A graph illustrating the result of the settings for the `mapout` and `curve`-attributes. In this case, a pattern of steps represents a musical scale where the white dot on the second step indicates which step the value currently is mapped to.

Recent projects have contributed to the development of WAXML in various ways [1, 12] and a feature that is extra useful for body movement sonification is the `speed`-property of `<var>` object values. It makes it possible to refer to the speed (the unsigned derivative value) of a movement directly without having to write the mathematical expression explicitly. To illustrate the feature, `value="$rightHand8x.speed"` would represent a value that

Figure 4: The outgoing value represented on the y-axis is the result of the mapping and the `convert`-attribute. In this case, this results in a frequency value in hertz. Time is represented on the x-axis with the current time on the right-hand side and the curve animating to the left.

reflects the right-hand horizontal speed similar to how a bow is moved to play a violin.

One weakness in WAXML that has been reported in earlier studies is the lack of debuggers for both the mapping process and the audio signal flow [9]. This led to the development of custom HTML elements⁵ for monitoring audio signals and variable values as a part of the preparation for this study. These can be seen in the lower-right of the screenshot in Figure 1 and include an oscilloscope, a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) graph, and a loudness meter. The variable monitor at the bottom includes three views that together reflect the mapping process in a `<var>` object reflected by the incoming values from `MediaPipe` (Fig. 2), a graph illustrating the mapping settings (Fig. 3), and finally, the value after mapping and conversion (Fig. 4).

4 Methods

The workshop was held during the Sound and Music Computing Summer School 2023 at the Royal College of Music in Stockholm⁶, where twenty doctoral and master students from the Sound and Music Computing community participated. They gave their consent for the data to be used anonymously for research purposes by the author of this paper.

The students were divided into three groups that subsequently visited the workshop for one hour. Each workshop began with a quick presentation of the platform, after which the participants worked through the six Sketches, one by one, led by the author of this paper. During the last 20 minutes, the participants were asked to pick one Sketch and alter it to their taste. It typically involved re-mappings such as selecting different body parts, modifying audio parameters like the frequency response of a low pass filter, or changing the list of note numbers in a musical scale.

After the workshop, the participants were invited to answer questions through an online form. The form contained questions about their age, occupation, and use of audio software, three Likert scale questions about their perception of the technology, and finally three free text questions about benefits, limitations, and suggestions for improvements. Observations during the workshop were also documented to capture how the work turned out in the classroom.

⁵<https://github.com/hanslindetorp/WebAudioXML/wiki/waxml-meter>

⁶<https://smcnetwork.org/smc2023/#summerschool>

5 Result

All participants managed to run through all six Sketches during the one-hour workshop and worked without major technical problems on their personal laptop computers. The performance differed between computers but never caused the audio to stop or glitch. The main challenge was that older computers automatically got a lower frame rate. The participants expressed this in terms of the computer being less responsive to their body movements. Overall, the workshop was a success and the platform was proven to meet all the specified design goals.

Fourteen participants completed the questions in the online form (13 PhD students and one master's student). They were asked what audio software they were using daily. In all, fourteen different audio applications were mentioned, and the participants reported using 1–4 different ones (1.8 on average). The most commonly used were Max/MSP⁷ that was used by half of the respondents, Reaper⁸ that was used by four, and Audacity⁹ that was used by three participants. The remaining eleven different applications were used by two or fewer users in the group.

The respondents were asked how likely they were to recommend WAXML as a language for educational, research, and artistic purposes. The answers were given using a Likert scale with five steps ranging from 'Not at all' to 'Very likely' and the result most clearly indicates a favor for educational use where 10 out of 14 said it was 'very likely' and the remaining answers were either towards 'very likely' (3 answers) or neutral (1 answer). The responses for research and artistic purposes were still on the positive side on the Likert scale (ranging from 1 to 5) even if not as strong as for educational purposes.

The participants were also asked to respond in free text to what they perceived as benefits, limitations, and important areas for improvement of the technology. Below is a summary of answers:

5.1 Benefits

The most appreciated aspects of the platform expressed in the answers were the accessibility and the ease with which it is possible to create a great result using advanced technologies in an online environment. E.g., *'It holds the hand of beginners, and presents them with rich results, that could likely encourage them to get deeper into real-time audio and creative coding.'* The integration with MediaPipe using the webcam was described as *'really nice'* and *'super convenient'*. When commenting on the language (WAXML) itself, the participants expressed appreciation for *'the easy syntax'* with *'good documentation'* that offered a *'freedom of parameter exploration'*. Several respondents also expressed an appreciation for XML as the base for the language while it *'uses something that is already established'* and that it *'unifies web syntax with HTML'*. To summarize the benefits of WAXML, one participant expressed that the platform *'allows non-programmer users to get fast into web-based music creation'*.

⁷<https://cycling74.com/products/max>

⁸<https://www.reaper.fm/>

⁹<https://www.audacityteam.org/>

5.2 Limitations

Three of the participants reported performance issues and that the platform sometimes *'feels somewhat unstable'* or *'not very responsive'*. Several answers expressed that the possibilities felt *'fairly limited'* and *'not exactly really programmable like SonicPI and Supercollider'*. Other areas where they experienced limitations were related to the coding environment where it was said to be *'hard to debug'* and that the platform didn't allow for *'live alteration of parameters without reloading'*. One participant expressed that *'more complex logic might be tricky, but if you want to do that then you should learn to program anyway!'*

5.3 Important areas for improvement

Finally, the answers captured valuable ideas for improvement. Some participants suggested that *'extensive web tutorials'*, *'more varied examples'*, and a *'big user base'* would contribute to making the platform even more useful. One participant was asking for OSC support and another a *'consistency of system response across OS'*. Several users were expressing ideas for how to improve the coding experience and were suggesting a *'correspondence table'* with available elements and a visual diagram of the rendered audio routing graph that *'could help people learn the environment'* and to avoid that WAXML *'hides the graph process of web audio a bit too much'*. Finally, some participants asked for features already existing in WAXML that were not explained during the workshop. These included the modular approach where audio components can be split into separate WAXML-scripts that can be shared and included in different projects.

6 Discussion

The result indicates in many ways that web technologies in general, and WAXML in particular, contribute to forming an accessible platform that is fast and easy to get started with. The participants perceive it as very useful, especially for educational purposes. The performance issues seem to be mostly old computers and will arguably become a lesser and lesser problem over time as performance increases for computers in general. With that being said, it could also be an interesting area for optimization of the platform.

Before drawing too many conclusions from the study, it is important to remember that the participants are experts in the field of audio software and many of them could easily relate to the task of mapping body movements to audio parameters even before the workshop. Their responses might therefore better be seen as coming from a potential teacher in the sonification field, rather than from a beginner when evaluating the platform for educational purposes.

The high representation of experience from graphical audio programming environments like Max/MSP might also have a positive impact on the participants' experience of WAXML, while the textual representation of audio objects in WAXML is similar to the structure found in Max/MSP and Pure Data. The fact that the participants are used to mapping data to audio parameters might also have an impact on how they perceive the data mapping syntax.

As the participants are postgraduate students in the field of sound and music computing, they could also be expected to be relatively experienced with mathematical expressions, programming languages, and numbers in general. It is worth noting that MediaPipe represents all values as floating points

where a position in the top-left corner of the screen is represented with (x:0.0, y:0.0) and bottom-right with (x:1.0, y:1.0) which means that a certain movement might be represented by values within a very small range. This might be easier for an experienced programmer to deal with than for a beginner.

It was interesting to see that the coding platform (p5.js) itself was not mentioned in any of the free-text answers, which might be a sign of it being a fairly transparent tool, doing what was expected. Arguably, though, some of the enthusiastic feedback regarding the easiness and accessibility can be attributed to p5.js even if not mentioned explicitly.

Observations during the workshop also led to some insights regarding how the participants interacted with the technology. Even if it was not mentioned, it could be noted that they adjusted their body movements according to the settings in the code rather than optimizing the settings to capture the movement better. One reason for this could be the process of having to repeatedly change and test to reach a good setting. A potential solution to the problem could be to introduce an auto-calibrating system where the user refers to values in percent of the present range of incoming values rather than having to specify exact values. Another observation was that the current syntax helps capture movements on one axis rather than a diagonal gesture which led to mappings using movements that were either horizontal or vertical. There are ways to solve this in the current version with a mathematical expression, but to include less experienced users, it should arguably become a built-in feature for future versions of WAXML.

Finally, the comment about the need for a big user base where audio components can easily be shared makes a lot of sense. This is arguably one of the most important benefits of web technologies in general and would be a crucial factor for whether a platform like the one presented in this study grows or not.

7 Conclusions

In this study, a new online platform for learning, creating, and sharing sonification applications has been presented. It was built with MediaPipe, p5.js, and WAXML to make the experience radically inclusive and accessible. The technology was tested and evaluated during a workshop with audio software experts. Observations and answers from an online form indicate that the technology meets the design goals and runs relatively smoothly on most computers during the one-hour workshop. The participants expressed their enthusiasm for the platform for primarily educational purposes and also pointed out some limitations and important areas for improvement, including interactive documentation and better tools for debugging. Observations also inspired important ideas about features for the next iteration of WAXML where variables are auto-calibrated and body movements easily recognized in multiple directions at different distances.

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